

August 2025

STATEMENT OF THE BOARD OF ALLEA IN ALIGNMENT WITH THE STANCE OF PROF. DAVID HAREL, PRESIDENT OF THE ISRAEL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

The ALLEA Board expresses its deep respect and full support for the [public statement](#) issued by Professor David Harel on July 14th 2025. He calls on the Israeli government to take immediate action to protect civilian lives in Gaza, restore health infrastructure, and allow unimpeded humanitarian aid – emphasising that doing so is both a moral imperative and a strategic necessity for Israel’s future international cooperation in science and research.

We stand in full solidarity with Professor Harel and share his deep concern over the humanitarian catastrophe unfolding in Gaza and the continued suffering of its civilian population. We unequivocally condemn the inhumane conditions caused by the ongoing conflict and call for an immediate and sustained resolution, as well as the release of all hostages still held by Hamas.

Our hearts and minds are with our member academy and with all who raise their voices in support of humanity, justice, and peace in this unbearable situation.

About ALLEA

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing approximately 60 academies from 40 countries in Europe. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on the European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines. Learn more here: <http://www.allea.org>.

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